

Vitrimers

Ludwik Leibler

Matière Molle et Chimie, ESPCI, Paris

Glass-workers shape marvelous objects without using moulds or precise temperature control because glass is a unique insoluble material that transforms from liquid to solid in a very progressive way. Vitrimers are organic materials that undergo glass-transition by molecular-network topology freezing and behave just like glass. They could profoundly affect many industries that rely on polymers and composites.